

Smart Home for Disabled People using IOT Technology

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Abstract From past few years, Internet of things (IOT) and smart homes are becoming popular day by day. Wireless system can be used in smart homes to facilitate disabled and handicapped people to make them autonomic and independent in their home environment. This paper shows the complete scheme of Smart Home using IOT technology with low cost, remote control, easy access, freedom of movement and wireless system. In proposed system, we have used IOT sensors and consider different aspects of a smart home which include security, comfort, and remote accessibility. The Android application is utilized to control and check status of sensors and home apparatuses. The standard control framework executes using smart phone. We developed the prototype in order to make IOT and smart home more practical.

Keywords— smart home, sensors, automation, Internet of Things

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart home is an advance technology which is helpful in daily life. By the help of smart home, we can control our entire home and can do our daily activities with ease. By the help of this technology we can make all electronic appliances to act smart. In our future this technology will become very helpful for people. All electrical appliances will take advantage of this technology. According to viewers the good aspect of this technology is that it will reduce the workload of people. Now a day this technology is implemented in whole house especially in kitchen and living room. It provides users with security, comfortable living and energy management features. It is very helpful for disabled persons [1].

This technology is made by the combination of different existing technologies. In this device a complex computer is installed to make it more functional and different. In a home both wired and wireless devices communicate with each other like DSL, Bluetooth, cable broadband etc. They provide a basis for smart home to operate [2].

The researchers have expected a smart connected home where multiple devices cooperatively work. In a home we can control lights, fans, camera, motors and locks. We can control light according to the weather and time of day.

Remotely we can also view a person who is at the door before unlocking it. It is predicted that in future smart home will contain about 15-30 connected devices and sensors. They all are linked through home area network and connected to internet [3].

Although the idea of home automation has been around for some time, actual smart homes have only existed a short while. This timeline focuses on hardware; meaning actual inventions leading up to the smart homes we know today and can expect from the near future.

In our work we used a concept of Wi-Fi chip because with the help of Wi-Fi multiple users are connecting at a time to use an android application. In early smart homes don't use a Wi-Fi connection to connect a device. It is using a Bluetooth and the drawback of Bluetooth is that it can connect only one user at a time.

1998 – Early 2000s – Smart Homes – Smart homes, or home automation, began to increase in reputation in the early 2000s. As such, different technology began to occur. Smart homes suddenly became a more reasonable option, and therefore a viable technology for consumers. Local technologies, home networking, and other devices began to appear on store shelves [4].

Today's Smart Homes – Today's smart homes are more about security and living greener. Smart home has made our life a lot easier than a decade ago. Our smart homes are maintainable, and they help to ensure that our homes aren't expending unnecessary energy. They also help alert us to intruders (whether we're home or not).

Current trends in smart home include remote mobile controlled lights, thermostat adjustment, scheduling appliances, mobile/email/text notifications, and remote video surveillance.

“Connectivity and interactivity are driving the way families live and manage their homes. So, while we are expected to be in more places due to business travel, children's school schedules and social activities, these new smart systems provide cutting edge connectivity to your household, even when you're far away. And when the house is occupied, the high level of control enables more convenience, control and safety from any part of your property. It all adds up to fewer worries and increased

enjoyment of life, which is something we would all welcome,” writes ADT technologies, who some say have lower home security costs than other competitors [5]. The structure is providing to disable and handicapped persons to fulfill their requirements in home. Also, it’s going to help save time of the people and they will be able to control their home remotely.

The objective is to build a base framework for Smart Home that can be centrally controlled using any device running android. We chose to show a lighting control system, temperature control and a security system as proof of concept. The framework makes it easier to integrate other such end applications.

- Control Home devices wirelessly
- Motion Detection and Security Alarm
- Status of sensors

II. Related work

Our related work will be thoroughly explained in this section. In the advancement of computer science, information technology and electronics we can conclude that energy can be generated from renewable resources [6]. We can utilize this energy for the management of home appliances. The current systems don’t concede the user for the feasibility to migrate power to home appliances. In the past, the electricity of the home appliances can be monitored and control with using plain power lines. Now, for the monitoring and controlling the home appliances ZigBee technology is used because it is portable.

In this paper the prestaton of sustainable energy source-based automation of home is given in which energy generation and energy consumption are two things. ZigBee can be used for the monitoring of home energy consumption and for energy generation power line communication (PLC) can be used. The server of home collects the data of energy consumption and generates the data of energy and analyzes the energy estimation and control the utilization of energy with respect to cost. The servers estimate the home energy data and make the useful statistical information by energy server. More efficient energy is saved, and cost reduction is given by this system. With the help of mobile app on Smartphone the electronic appliances can be save; see the flow and electricity problem can be determined [7].

Home automation based on voice recognition system have many challenges like people are suffering from paraplegia or quadriplegia (can speak and listen but can’t move limbs) to handle the many home devices and impel bed height by voice commands [8].

The system which is proposed is consisting of Arduino microcontroller, adjustable bed, relay circuit and the voice recognition system. This system of voice recognition required training. It can be successful via circuit relay in Arduino devices [9].

The adaptable bed elevation system has three various modes by user need and luxury. In various conditions the accuracy of voice recognition system can be measured.

The Home Automation System (HAS) [10] is intended aimed at cellular phones having Android framework to mechanize a 8 bit Bluetooth coordinate which directions various home machines like fan, knobs, light and numerous additionally utilizing on/off dispatch.

This automatic methodology of utilizing microcontroller for directing the gadgets in domestic that could facilitate the errands of utilizing the customary technique for the switch. The maximum celebrated and productive innovation for little variety remote correspondence Bluetooth is utilized here to robotize the framework [11]. The HAS framework for Android user is a stage to simplicity of the undertakings by monitoring one to twenty-four distinct apparatuses in many kinds of home-based atmosphere.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this section we will discuss about the working of our project. When the MCU get a signal from a user it will activate the required pin. This means if the user sends a command to chip to activate any of the four devices, it will activate that device. The chip will keep sending the inputs given by the motion sensor and the temperature + humidity sensor to the user for display.

Figure 1: Architectural view of the system

Device Working

When the user will press the button of device in application or from webpage of server, it will send a command to activate the pin of chip, when that pin will be active, voltage and current will pass thought this point to the IC, where this point will be used as an input. The IC we have used have inputs and outputs right in front of each other. So, when any input will be active its corresponding output will be active and through that output the relay will switch. Every relay has a connector next to it, one point of every connector is common which means that voltage will be remain on one point of every device. The other point of connector will already have voltage on it, so when the common point of any device will get a high signal, it will turn on the switch and the device will get power from both points of connectors.

DHT Sensor Status

In our circuit we have treated the sensors as inputs. The DHT sensor will send data though the data line to the Chip which will keep sending it to the user until that user is connected to the server [12].

Motion and alarm

We have used PIR motion sensor which work on 180 degree. This means it will detect any motion on 180 degree. Its status will not be active unless a motion is detected. When it detects a motion, it will send its status to the chip and also it will activate the buzzer. The chip will

send the status data to the user and user will see a red line "Motion detected".

Arduino IDE

The Arduino IDE is open source software that is used to compose a code and upload a code to the chip. We are used this software to compose a code of sensors in a chip which are used in this interface. We are used different sensors e.g. Humidity sensor, temperature sensor, PIR motion sensor etc. All these sensor codes are written in this software. This software is easy to make write or compose a code [13].

Writing Sketches

combined operating schemes of Arduino Software (IDE) are called sketches. These demonstrations are collected in the satisfied apparatus and are secure through the best extension.no: The writing administrator takes focuses designed for Critical /sticking and used for observing contented. The communication zone affords blame though limited then transfer out and displays errors. Complete error messages and other data can be producing by Arduino Studio which shows the results. In the base of right-hand corner there is a window which show sequential port and design board.

Android Studio

The Android SDK was produced utilizing the Java programming dialect. Correspondingly, Android applications are likewise created utilizing java [14]. Thus, the Java Development Kit (JDK) is the primary segment that must be introduced. Android improvement needs the establishment of form 8 of the Ordinary Version of the Java Program Development Kit. Java is given in both improvement (JDK) and runtime (JRE) bundles. For the reasons for Android advancement, the JDK must be installed.

Figure 2: Android Application when motion is not detected

Figure 3: Motion detection in Android Application

A brilliant home is one of the thoughts that individuals committed both cash and time to achieve the consummately savvy. As tasks around there expanded the will to push ahead and present further developed advances showed up. An extensive variety of advances were proposed and tested. They principally vary with respect to the reason and focus of the keen framework. The greater part of the advancements utilized in Smart Homes have been initially utilized in different regions; others have been created exceptionally to satisfy the desires for a Smart Home framework. Amid the improvement procedure creators have achieved a propelled organize in home mechanization, security and human services. Anyway, confinements show up regarding knowledge, programmed control and planning a Smart Home with an extensive variety of highlights that can cover distinctive parts of clients' needs [15]. Our examination venture empowers an outline that joins a significant part of the above in a similar framework. The created model comprises of the product interfaces that empower the clients to oversee, control and access the entire framework. Incorporated inside the product is the neural systems and different parts of the framework to be points of interest promote in this paper [16]. On the equipment side, the model incorporated the control and the observing units, keen caution frameworks, and a few sensors utilized in the paper.

Figure 4: Smart home circuit diagram

TESTING

This section includes testing images of our research. What was the reaction of circuit when we applied a certain action?

The buzzer will initialize and will produce a sound.

Figure 5: Testing of system's circuit for the

Figure 6: Status of android application after power up

When we click on device one it will turn on the light 1 and 1st LED on the circuit will be on as shown in the image.

Figure 7: Testing of device (LED)

Now when any motion is detected it will show us following view of the application and buzzer will produce a noise that motion is detected.

Figure 8: Detection of motion using android app

ESP 8266 12F ELEMENT

The ESP8266 12F Wi-Fi element is a free SOC by corresponding TCP/IP standard that be able to provide more controlled entry to your Wi-Fi arrange. The ESP8266 12F is capable toward each simplifying a function or unloading all Wi-Fi establishing capabilities after alternative appliance workstation. Each element of this module segment makes pre-customized with an AT order set forward, which ways, you can essentially assign this to your Arduino appliance and become around as much Wi-Fi- ability as a Wi-Fi defense suggestion [17]. The ESP8266 module is an amazingly financially savvy board with an enormous, and constantly emerging, network. This system has a ground-breaking enough on-load up behavior and size capability that assists it to be synchronized with the sensors and other appliance specific devices over its GPIOs with slight enhancement ahead and irrelevant assembling among on the spot.

Figure 9: Wi-Fi Module for the Arduino

Hardware components which are used to create the smart home as following:

- Voltage regulator
- IC
- Diode
- Relays
- Connector
- Resistors
- Transistor
- PIR Motion sensor
- DHT 11 sensor
- Buzzer
- USB serial port
- jumper

VI. Conclusion

We proposed a careful and effective brilliant home utilizing an Android working framework as the rising innovations utilized in mechanization region. The framework has 2 equipment parts: a neighborhood gadget to exchange signs to home machines, and a versatile smart gadget running Android application. The functionalities of

every segment of the framework is clarified, and the correspondence foundations of the parts are likewise clarified.

We did face some issues and limitations while working on this project. The one of the major limitations was despite being a low-cost chip, we can control a limited number of devices and sensors using this Wi-Fi module because it has limited number of pins, but this limitation can be removed by using this module with a much larger and complicated circuit. Another limitation was the PIR motion sensor as it detects motion on 180 degree. We have set its sensitivity but still it will show detection with even a small movement.

VII. Future Aspects

Smart home is becoming a part of today's life and as technology is changing overnight so is the point of view about technology. They are more interested in making their life easier, comfortable and time saving. We will continue working on this project for further development. We will use a public IP so that the user will be able to control his home from anywhere around the world, beside public IP we will develop an IOS application and so that IOS user can also use this service without using browser.

In our further development we will introduce security cameras and their live feed will be viewable inside user application.

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